

Some Adducts of Simple and Mixed Alkoxides of Antimony(v) with Ammonia and Pyridine

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Adducts of the types $[\text{Sb}(\text{OR})_5\text{B}]$ ($\text{R}=\text{CH}_3, \text{C}_2\text{H}_5, \text{iC}_3\text{H}_7, \text{iC}_4\text{H}_7$; $\text{B}=\text{NH}_3$ and $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$) and $[\text{Sb}(\text{OR})_3(\text{OR}')_2\text{NH}_3]$ ($\text{R}=\text{iC}_3\text{H}_7, \text{iC}_4\text{H}_7$; $\text{R}'=\text{CH}_3$ and iC_2H_5) have been prepared under strictly anhydrous conditions by the reactions of SbCl_5 or $\text{Sb}(\text{OR})_3\text{Br}_2$ with alcohols in the presence of anhydrous ammonia or pyridine. The adducts are highly soluble in parent alcohols but are hydrolytically as well as thermally unstable even under reduced pressure. Molecular weight measurements indicate their monomeric nature in parent alcohols. Conductometric studies suggest that they are covalent in character. An octahedral structure of the adducts has been proposed on the basis of ir, ^1H and ^{13}C nmr studies.

IN comparison to antimony(III) alkoxides, antimony(v) alkoxides should exhibit greater Lewis acid character in forming stable 6-coordinate adducts with bases. However, except for the preliminary reports of a few adducts¹⁻⁴ of antimony(v) alkoxides, viz. $[\text{Sb}(\text{OEt})_5\text{NH}_3]$, $[\text{Sb}(\text{OEt})_5\text{Et}_2\text{NH}]$, $[\text{Sb}(\text{OPr}^i)_5\text{NH}_3]$ and $[\text{Sb}(\text{OPh})_5\text{NH}_3]$, little is known about their chemistry. In the present communication, we report the synthesis and properties of some more adducts of simple as well as mixed alkoxides of antimony(v) with anhydrous ammonia and pyridine.

Experimental

Antimony(III) alkoxides and bromine were distilled before use. Molecular weights of the derivatives were determined in parent alcohols using a Gallenkamp ebullimeter. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra on a JEOL FX 90Q spectrometer.

As all the adducts were synthesised under strictly anhydrous conditions by a similar procedure, syntheses of only two representative adducts are described below :

$\text{Sb}(\text{OPr}^i)_3(\text{OMe})_2\text{NH}_3$: Bromine (1.59 g, 20.0 mmol) in benzene (~15 ml) was added to antimony(III) isopropoxide (2.97 g, 10.0 mmol) in benzene (~20 ml). The reaction was exothermic and vigorous and the contents were refluxed for 1 h. Excess methanol (~15 ml) was then added and the contents were again refluxed for 1 h. Dry ammonia gas was then passed into the above mixture at room temperature. An exothermic

reaction occurred and the passage of ammonia was continued till the mixture cooled down to room temperature. The resulting precipitated ammonium bromide was filtered off and the excess of solvent was removed from the filtrate under reduced pressure, yielding a brown solid (98%) (Table 1).

$\text{Sb}(\text{OPr}^i)_5\text{NH}_3$: Slow addition with continuous stirring of an ice-cold solution of freshly distilled SbCl_5 (2.47 g, 8.3 mmol) in chloroform (~10 ml) to an excess of Pr^iOH resulted in an exothermic reaction. To this mixture, dry ammonia gas was passed till it cooled down to room temperature. The precipitated ammonium chloride was filtered off and the excess solvent was removed under reduced pressure to give a light brown solid (86%) which was purified by recrystallisation from Pr^iOH (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

Adducts of the type $[\text{Sb}(\text{OR})_5\text{B}]$ have been prepared by the reaction of anhydrous SbCl_5 in chloroform with an alcohol at 0° in the presence of a base (B) under strictly anhydrous conditions,

where $\text{B} = \text{NH}_3, \text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$; $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3, \text{C}_2\text{H}_5, \text{iC}_3\text{H}_7$ and iC_4H_7 .

Adducts of mixed alkoxy derivatives of antimony(v) of the type $[\text{Sb}(\text{OR})_3(\text{OR}')_2\text{NH}_3]$ have been prepared by the reaction of $\text{Sb}(\text{OR})_3\text{Br}_2$ (prepared *in situ*) with alcohols in the presence of anhydrous

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TABLE 1 - SYNTHESIS, ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA

SbCl ₅ g/(mmol)	Br ₂ in g/(mmol)	Compd.	Yields %	Nature	Mol. wt. Found/ (Calcd.)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				
						Sb	Alkoxy	N	C	H
6.01 (20.07)	-	[Sb(OMe) ₅ .NH ₃]	92	White crystal	534 (294)	42.43 (41.45)	-	2.99 (4.77)	18.98 (20.42)	6.01 (5.11)
5.77 (19.28)	-	[Sb(OMe) ₅ .C ₅ H ₅ N]	92	Brown solid	437 (350)	33.40 (34.22)	-	-	32.89 (33.73)	6.47 (5.62)
5.95 (19.88)	-	[Sb(OEt) ₅ .NH ₃]	93	Brown solid	-	32.59 (33.47)	-	2.25 (3.85)	31.97 (32.99)	8.56 (7.69)
2.48 (19.29)	-	[Sb(OPri) ₅ .NH ₃]	88	Brown solid	551 (434)	27.44 (28.06)	67.61 (68.01)	2.69 (3.23)	40.87 (41.49)	9.36 (8.76)
3.89 (12.99)	-	[Sb(OPri) ₅ .C ₅ H ₅ N]	90	Brown solid	575 (496)	25.06 (24.56)	55.89 (59.51)	-	47.90 (48.41)	7.71 (8.07)
4.04 (13.50)	-	[Sb(OiAm) ₅ .NH ₃]	89	Brown liquid	-	20.13 (21.22)	-	1.98 (2.44)	-	-
Sb(OPri) ₅ 2.97 (9.94)	1.59 (19.87)	[Sb(OPri) ₃ (OMe) ₂ .NH ₃]	98	Brown solid	464 (378)	32.75 (32.23)	-	2.65 (3.71)	34.19 (34.94)	6.78 (7.15)
Sb(OiAm) ₅ 2.18 (5.69)	0.29 (11.37)	[Sb(OAmi) ₅ (OMe) ₂ .NH ₃]	90	White solid	522 (462)	25.36 (26.37)	-	2.69 (3.03)	43.63 (44.18)	8.29 (9.09)
1.98 (5.17)	0.83 (0.37)	[Sb(OiAm) ₅ (OPri) ₂ .NH ₃]	86	Brown solid	473 (518)	22.76 (23.51)	-	2.00 (2.70)	47.97 (48.67)	10.81 (9.66)

TABLE 2 - IR SPECTRAL DATA* (cm⁻¹) OF ADDUCTS OF ANTIMONY(V) ALKOXIDES

Compd.	Sym. stret. C-O	Sym. stret. Sb-O	Antisym stret Sb-O	Sym. bend Sb-OC	Antisym bend Sb-OC and stret. Sb-N
[Sb(OCH ₃) ₅ .NH ₃]	1 040br	580br	503br	450m	-
[Sb(OC ₂ H ₅) ₅ .NH ₃]	1 050br	600s	550br	430w	330br
[Sb(OiC ₃ H ₇) ₅ .NH ₃]	1 110br	615br	530br	450m	310br
[Sb(OiC ₄ H ₉) ₅ .NH ₃]	1 070br	560br	560br	425br	300vw
[Sb(OCH ₃) ₅ .C ₅ H ₅ N]	1 100br	615vs	545m	425m	280br
[Sb(OiC ₃ H ₇) ₅ .C ₅ H ₅ N]	1 080m	590br	550vw	430s	360br, 330w
[Sb(OiC ₃ H ₇) ₅ (OCH ₃) ₂ .NH ₃]	1 070vs	-	560br	450m	280br
[Sb(OC ₂ H ₅) ₅ (OCH ₃) ₂ .NH ₃]	1 050br	-	520br	400s	330w
[Sb(OC ₂ H ₅) ₅ (OC ₂ H ₅) ₂ .NH ₃]	1 050br	610vw	-	405br	330vw

vs=very strong, s=strong, m=medium, w=weak, vw=very weak, br=broad.

ammonia,

All these adducts are coloured except [Sb(OMe)₅.NH₃] and [Sb(OAmi)₅(OMe)₂.NH₃], which are white solids and [Sb(OAm)₅.NH₃], which is a brown viscous liquid. These are highly soluble in parent alcohols and sparingly soluble in other organic solvents. They are non-volatile and tend to decompose on heating even under reduced pressure. Conductivity measurements in parent alcohols exhibit their non-electrolytic behaviour.

Molecular weight determinations of the adducts suggest that they undergo varying degree of

dissociation in refluxing parent alcohols. This observation is in agreement with the results reported⁸ earlier on derivatives of lower boiling alcohols of the type [Sb(OR)₅.ROH] showing a strong tendency of associations, when the molecular weights were measured cryoscopically.

Important ir spectral data for these derivatives are summarised in Table 2. The results have been compared with those of the corresponding vibrational spectra of Sb(OR)₃^{7,8} and Sb(OR)Cl₂^{1-4,9}. Bands observed in the region 1 110-940 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to SbO-C stretching vibrations. Similarly bands at 615-560 and 530-520 cm⁻¹ may be ascribed to symmetric and antisymmetric stretching vibrations of Sb-OC bond respectively. Bands at 450-400 cm⁻¹ could be assigned to Sb-OC symmetric bending vibrations. Generally broad bands appear in the region 340-280 cm⁻¹ which might be due to a combination of symmetric stretching vibrations of Sb-N and antisymmetric bending vibrations of SbO-C.

TABLE 3 - ^1H AND ^{13}C NMR SPECTRAL DATA (δ ppm) OF ADDUCTS OF ANTIMONY(V)

Compd.	Nuclei	CH_3	CH_2	CH_2O	CHO	C-H	NH_2 or $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}$
$[\text{Sb}(\text{OCH}_3)_5 \text{NH}_2]^a$	^1H ^{13}C	3.51s 50.82					7.44s
$[\text{Sb}(\text{OCH}_3)_5 \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}]^a$	^1H ^{13}C	3.67s 45.08					8.09m 145.51
$[\text{Sb}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_5 \cdot \text{NH}_3]^a$	^1H ^{13}C	1.57br 18.64		4.03br 60.14			7.69br
$[\text{Sb}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_5 \cdot \text{NH}_3]^b$	^1H	1.14d			3.93h		7.53br
$[\text{Sb}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_5 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}]^b$	^1H	1.15d			3.93h		8.04br
$[\text{Sb}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_5 \cdot \text{NH}_3]^c$	^1H ^{13}C	0.85d 22.43	1.32m	3.51t 61.27		1.68br 24.65	7.26d
$[\text{Sb}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_5 (\text{OCH}_3)_2 \cdot \text{NH}_3]^a$	^{13}C	50.76				65.10	
$[\text{Sb}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_5 (\text{OCH}_3)_2 \cdot \text{NH}_3]^a$	^{13}C	25.14					
$[\text{Sb}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_5 (\text{OCH}_3)_2 \cdot \text{NH}_3]^a$	^{13}C	58.40	41.66	61.27		24.65	

^a CDCl_3 , ^b CCl_4 .

s = singlet, d = doublet, t = triplet, h = heptat, m = multiplet and br = broad.

In case of dimeric compounds of the type $\text{Sb}(\text{OR})\text{Cl}_4$, bands observed at $515 - 495 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ have been assigned to $\text{Sb}-\text{O} \rightarrow \text{Sb}$ vibrations. Absence of these bands in the ir spectra of all the above adducts appears to confirm the monomeric nature of these products. In case of adducts of mixed alkoxy derivatives, $[\text{Sb}(\text{OR})_5(\text{OR}')_2 \cdot \text{B}]$, ir spectra appear to be of little help in characterising the presence of two types of alkoxy groups.

^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectral data of the adducts have been recorded at room temperature (Table 3). ^1H nmr spectra exhibit only one type of signals at room temperature, which have been assigned to the terminal alkoxy groups. The integration ratio corresponds to the number of the chemically different types of protons in these adducts of antimony(v) alkoxydes. ^1H nmr signals in the adducts show a downfield shift (~ 0.8 ppm) as compared to those observed in the free alcohols¹⁰.

Fig. 1

Similarly, ^{13}C nmr spectra show the presence of the expected number of signals corresponding to

the number of chemically different types of carbon atoms present in these adducts. Downfield chemical shifts of ^{13}C nuclei in these adducts have been observed when compared with those of the free alcohols¹⁰. Based on the above studies an octahedral structure (Fig 1) may be suggested.

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